

DIPLOM

"USE OF ICT IN TEACHING IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM"

TORAYEV JAHANGIR

"Pedagogs" is awarded by the editorial board of the international electronic journal

Editor-in-Chief: A.B.Vahobov

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